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Proactive community adaptation to climate change
through social transformation and behavioural change

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D2.1 Baseline Assessment and Knowledge Gathering for the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
QHM	Quadruple Helix Model
THM	Triple Helix Model

Executive summary

The PRO-CLIMATE project aims to empower communities in adapting to climate change by fostering social transformation, behavioural change, and improved governance. Central to this initiative is the establishment of six Living Labs (LLs) located in Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Badajoz (Spain), Bergen (Norway), Gdańsk (Poland), and Zakynthos (Greece). These Living Labs serve as platforms for co-creation, enabling diverse stakeholders to collaborate in addressing local climate resilience challenges.

A baseline assessment was conducted to evaluate the starting conditions and implementation readiness of each Living Lab. This assessment highlights the significant diversity across the six locations, reflecting differences in environmental, social, economic, and institutional contexts. While some Living Labs, such as those in Gdańsk and Zakynthos, display high levels of maturity and progress in climate action, others, including Leipzig, Badajoz, and Bergen, require additional foundational support to establish effective structures and engage stakeholders. The findings reveal that most Living Labs excel in defining objectives and selecting practices relevant to their contexts. However, common challenges include gaps in operational knowledge and expertise in demonstrating systems, evaluating performance, and scaling up solutions. These areas of development are critical to ensuring the long-term success and sustainability of the Living Labs. To address these challenges, the PRO-CLIMATE project emphasises a flexible and adaptive implementation approach, tailored to the unique conditions of each Living Lab. Operational plans will be customized to align with local needs, ensuring meaningful progress toward climate resilience. Capacity-building initiatives will play a pivotal role, including training programs on co-creation methodologies, citizen science initiatives, public awareness campaigns, and strategies to integrate policies and strengthen collaboration among stakeholders. These efforts aim to close knowledge gaps, promote networking and knowledge transfer, and establish robust monitoring and evaluation systems.

Living Labs in the PRO-CLIMATE project are conceptualised as open innovation ecosystems operating in real-life settings. They are characterised by active user involvement, multi-stakeholder collaboration, and iterative feedback mechanisms to create sustainable impacts. The project adopts the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) to engage key actors from academia, industry, government, and civil society, fostering a systemic approach to climate adaptation. Data management for the baseline assessment adhered to the FAIR principles, ensuring that information is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Data collection was conducted through baseline questionnaires and bilateral meetings with Living Lab representatives. Despite these efforts, limitations such as variability in co-creation methodologies, inconsistencies in governance metrics, and potential gaps in baseline data were identified and will be addressed in subsequent phases.

The expertise of the PRO-CLIMATE consortium, spanning research, social transformation, behavioural change, and systems analysis, is strategically distributed across Work Packages to support the Living Labs' development and sustainability. Addressing capacity-building needs and operational gaps, the project aims to ensure that the Living Labs become effective, long-lasting platforms for climate resilience, contributing significantly to the broader goals of sustainable development.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background of the PRO-CLIMATE Project

The strategic objective of PRO-CLIMATE is to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. The outputs of PRO-CLIMATE will include: a) the identification of key components of climate adaptation systems, their interactions, systemic interdependencies and trade-offs, b) the design, implementation, and evaluation of a Living Lab framework, c) the identification of social tipping points and leverage actions for policy makers, d) the development of a multi-agent computer model for European socio-ecological systems to allow a realistic analysis of existing and future policy scenarios likely to produce systemic transformations, and e) policy recommendations to accelerate systemic change.

1.2 Importance of Living Labs in achieving climate resilience

PRO-CLIMATE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of six Living Labs (LLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance climate resilience and achieve systemic transformations through behavioural change and good governance. The six (6) Living Labs involved in the project are: Sligo, Ireland; Leipzig, Germany; Badajoz, Spain; Bergen, Norway; Gdansk, Poland; Zakynthos, Greece.

Within PRO-CLIMATE, WP2 objectives are to design and implement the Living Lab framework in order to create a real-life testing environment for co-creation and co-design of climate adaptation strategies, to contextualise the Living Lab framework for each case study and develop and implement the pilot operational plans in each Living Lab, to coordinate and manage all Living Lab workshops, tasks, meetings, and activities in order to support the WPs 2-6, to produce knowledge and data that can be used to inform policy and create systemic transformation through effective governance, to gather knowledge on individual behaviours, to transform individual behaviours through effective stakeholder engagement, to ensure knowledge exchange between the Living Labs within the project, and other EU projects and Living Labs, and to ensure the sustainability of the Living Lab beyond the project, through policy-changes and other measures.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the baseline assessment

This deliverable (D2.1) outlines an overall framework and methodology to set up the Living Labs for each case study. It is structured as follows. First, the overall methodology and approach to design the framework is presented in Section 2. Then, in Section 3 the framework for setting up Living Labs is explained. Following, the baseline knowledge (Section 4) as well as its implementation process (Section 5) is addressed. Finally, the document concludes with the main highlights of the deliverable and the next steps in WP2.

2 Methodology

2.1 Overview of the literature

Living Labs (LLs) are increasingly recognized as effective platforms for addressing complex urban challenges through collaborative, human-centred approaches. Brown and Katz (2011) highlight the role of design thinking in structuring creative problem-solving processes, emphasising the importance of stakeholder engagement in co-creation. This aligns with the findings of Leminen et al. (2012), who describe LLs as open-innovation ecosystems where actors from diverse sectors, including citizens, collaborate to drive innovation and develop sustainable solutions.

Mastelic's (2019) Living Lab Integrative Process further supports this framework, proposing a phased methodology for building climate resilience by combining problem identification with iterative solution testing. Similarly, Puerari et al. (2018) emphasise that co-creation in LLs requires continuous stakeholder interaction to align objectives and incorporate local knowledge effectively into the solutions developed. Schuurman et al. (2017) underscore the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration, noting that the active participation of diverse actors enhances the relevance and quality of innovations within LLs.

Leal Filho et al. (2023) further extend the discussion by situating Living Labs within the framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). They highlight how LLs provide innovative solutions to sustainability challenges by fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and aligning local actions with global objectives.

These studies collectively highlight that LLs are more than experimental environments; they are structured and inclusive platforms for iterative innovation aimed at urban sustainability. The PRO-CLIMATE project integrates these insights into its methodology, leveraging design thinking, open innovation, and co-creation principles to ensure that its Living Labs are responsive to local needs, inclusive of diverse perspectives, and capable of fostering long-term climate resilience.

2.2 Approach to Designing the Framework

The PRO-CLIMATE project's framework for Living Labs (LLs) is a co-creation-driven approach aimed at building climate resilience in six case studies. It follows a structured methodology, grounded in the Living Lab Integrative Process, which progresses through eight phases—from problem identification to solution deployment and scale-up (fig. 1). This process, adapted from Mastelic (2019), emphasises human-centric innovation, design thinking, and stakeholder engagement to ensure solutions are context-specific, socially relevant, and technically sound.

Figure 1 Non-linear Process of Design Thinking (Source: Interaction Design Foundation Interaction-design.org)

Key tools supporting the framework include a Living Lab training program, a toolkit for implementation, and tailored operational plans (POPs) that guide the actions of each LL based on local needs. These tools equip stakeholders with the knowledge and skills to implement climate resilience strategies while ensuring flexibility to adapt to diverse socio-environmental conditions across case studies.

A core strength of the framework lies in its emphasis on sustainability and scalability, with the added phases of implementation and scale-up ensuring that innovations can be applied beyond the project’s lifespan. Fostering bottom-up engagement and integrating local knowledge, the framework is designed to create long-lasting, adaptable solutions for climate change challenges in urban environments.

2.3 Data Collection Methods

The PRO-CLIMATE project utilised a variety of data collection methods to ensure that each Living Lab (LL) could be properly assessed and contextualized. These methods were designed to gather information at different stages of the project, allowing the project team to refine operational strategies and ensure that the LL framework was responsive to the unique needs of each case study. The primary methods included online questionnaires, bilateral meetings, and workshops, deployed sequentially to support the overall methodological approach.

2.3.1 Online Questionnaire

An online questionnaire was a fundamental component of the data collection process, offering a structured means to gather insights from the six cases involved in the PRO-CLIMATE project. A questionnaire was conducted within the first six months of the project to update the initial assessment. This survey aimed to assess the progress made since the project’s inception,

particularly in relation to the co-creation processes initiated in the LLs. Assessing the needs and capacities of each Living Lab, the project team could ensure that the LL framework and methodology being developed remained relevant and flexible enough to address new challenges or evolving conditions.

The questionnaire design was informed by inputs from the leaders of the various Work Packages (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5), ensuring alignment with the broader objectives of the project. The survey covered a wide range of topics, including:

- **Living Lab objectives:** Each LL's specific goals for creating and operating the Living Lab, with a focus on expected outcomes related to climate resilience.
- **Expected outcomes and stakeholders:** The intended results of each LL's activities, and identification of potential stakeholders, including local governments, community organisations, and private sector actors.
- **Technical and financial capacities:** An assessment of each LL's existing resources, including technical expertise and financial support, to ensure the feasibility of their planned activities.
- **Experience in relevant projects:** Previous involvement in climate adaptation and related projects, helping to identify cases with more advanced capabilities and those that might require additional support.
- **Expertise in key Work Package areas:** The cases were asked to self-assess their level of expertise in relation to key project areas, including WP2 (LL framework design), WP3 (social transformation), WP4 (community behavioural change), and WP5 (systems analysis for climate resilience). This information was critical for identifying gaps that needed to be addressed through training or capacity-building efforts.

The online questionnaire was distributed using an online platform that facilitated both distribution and collection of responses. The use of digital surveys allowed for a standardised approach across all cases while providing flexibility for respondents to complete the survey at their convenience. This method also ensured a comprehensive data set that could be easily analysed using quantitative and qualitative methods.

2.3.2 Bilateral Meetings

In addition to the online questionnaires, a series of bilateral meetings were conducted between June and August 2024. These meetings served as a critical follow-up step, enabling direct communication between the project team and representatives from each Living Lab. The meetings were held online, ensuring that all cases could participate regardless of geographic location or logistical constraints.

The primary goal of the bilateral meetings was to further contextualise the data collected from the online questionnaires. During these meetings, the project team worked with each LL to define specific needs, objectives, and expected outcomes based on the local context. This was essential for tailoring the Living Lab framework to each case study's unique environmental, social, and economic conditions. The meetings also provided an opportunity to:

- Identify the **current phase of each LL** in relation to the overall framework. This helped clarify where each case study was in terms of problem definition, stakeholder engagement, and strategy development.
- Define **specific activities and milestones** required for each LL to progress through the framework. This included identifying key stakeholders, planning co-creation sessions, and setting timelines for the implementation of pilot operational plans (POPs).
- Address any **gaps or challenges** highlighted during the questionnaire phase, including technical or financial limitations, and explore potential solutions or support mechanisms available within the PRO-CLIMATE project.

These meetings were highly interactive and allowed for in-depth discussions tailored to the individual needs of each Living Lab. Involving living labs' representatives from each case study in the conversation, the project team ensured that the plans developed were both realistic and aligned with local priorities. This process of continuous feedback and iteration is a hallmark of the Living Lab methodology, which emphasises co-creation and human-centric innovation.

The meetings were documented, and the insights gathered were used to refine the overall LL framework, ensuring that it remained adaptable and inclusive to the diverse range of cases involved in the project. Additionally, the results from the bilateral meetings were instrumental in preparing for the workshops that followed, providing a foundation for more focused, collaborative efforts to address specific climate resilience challenges in each case study.

2.3.3 Workshops

Workshops are a key component of the Living Lab (LL) methodology, designed to engage stakeholders in co-creation activities to collaboratively address challenges identified earlier in the project. During the initial phase, online workshops with LL representatives have already employed several facilitation tools, including design thinking exercises, stakeholder mapping, and scenario planning. These tools have proven effective in fostering creative problem-solving, identifying key actors, and exploring future climate scenarios.

Building on these foundations, the next phase of the project will extend these methodologies into physical workshops (at least three workshops/LL), bringing together a broader range of LL stakeholders. These in-person sessions will allow for deeper collaboration and direct engagement with local actors, ensuring the strategies developed are contextually relevant and actionable. Each workshop will be tailored to the specific needs of the LL, focusing on local climate resilience challenges and potential solutions.

The workshops will employ a variety of facilitation techniques, including:

- **Design Thinking Exercises:** To encourage innovative approaches to complex problems.
- **Stakeholder Mapping Sessions:** To refine understanding of the roles and responsibilities of key actors in implementing climate adaptation strategies.
- **Scenario Planning:** To evaluate the robustness of different strategies under varying climate change scenarios.

The results from these workshops will feed directly into the development of Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) for each LL. This phased approach ensures that the strategies co-created are, not only innovative, but also practical, aligned with local needs, and capable of delivering long-term climate resilience.

2.4 Analysis Methods and Tools

To analyse the baseline data collected through online questionnaires and bilateral meetings, the PRO-CLIMATE project adopted a comprehensive framework built on the ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs) approach (fig. 2). This method not only provided a standardised framework for evaluating the maturity and readiness of each Living Lab (LL), but also incorporated the unique characteristics, challenges, and opportunities present in each case study. This tailored approach allowed for a holistic evaluation, ensuring that the Living Labs' operational strategies were context-sensitive and grounded in the real-world capacities of the cases involved (Enoll, 2017).

What is a Living Lab?

A Living Lab is a user-centric innovation environment, built on realistic activities and research where all relevant partners are involved in open processes, with objective to generate sustainable values for LL partners and stakeholders.

Figure 2 What is a Living Lab according to ENoLL approach? (Source: European Network of Living Labs, ENoLL)

2.4.1 ENoLL Approach

The ENoLL framework, which is widely recognised as a leading model for fostering innovation in Living Lab environments, was adapted to suit the specific needs of the PRO-CLIMATE project. This adaptation was essential for addressing the distinct environmental, social, and institutional contexts of the cases involved. The ENoLL methodology supports a participatory and human-centric innovation process, ensuring that all relevant stakeholders are involved in co-creating solutions that address local challenges, particularly those posed by climate change.

In applying this framework, the PRO-CLIMATE project aimed to assess the strengths, weaknesses, gaps, and development areas of each Living Lab in terms of their climate resilience and stakeholder engagement capacities. Through this structured analysis, the project team was able to:

- **Evaluate the Living Labs' maturity:** This involved assessing how developed each LL was in terms of its ability to engage stakeholders, co-create climate resilience solutions, and implement them in real-world settings.
- **Identify key enablers and barriers:** The ENoLL approach helped in identifying the factors that could either facilitate or hinder the successful establishment and operation of the LLs. Enablers often included active local governance, strong stakeholder networks, and technical expertise. Barriers could include limited financial resources, low stakeholder engagement, or a lack of technical infrastructure.
- **Design responsive operational plans:** The analysis results were directly used to inform the creation of Pilot Operational Plans (POPs), which were tailored to the specific needs and capacities of each case study. These plans provided clear pathways for implementing co-created climate resilience strategies.

2.4.2 Integration with Mastellic's ULL Process

To enhance the analytical rigor, the ENoLL approach was integrated with Mastellic's (2019) Urban Living Lab (ULL) Integrative Process. This provided an additional layer of analysis, ensuring that the LLs followed a well-defined process from identifying climate-related problems to deploying practical solutions. The integration also allowed for flexibility, recognising that the conditions and challenges each case study faced would require adaptation at different stages of the LL process (fig. 3).

Figure 3 Living Lab interactive process according to Mastellic's (Source: Mastellic, 2019)

The ULL framework outlines eight core phases, which guide the progression from the problem definition to solution deployment. In the PRO-CLIMATE project, this process was expanded to include two additional steps—implementation and scale-up—thus ensuring that the outcomes of the Living Lab interventions could be sustained and replicated across other contexts, both within and outside the project.

2.4.3 Phases of the LL Framework (Adapted from Mastellic, 2019)

- **Problem Definition:** The first phase involves identifying the specific climate-related challenges facing each case study. This includes understanding environmental vulnerabilities, such as sea-level rise, erosion, and flooding, as well as the socio-economic impacts of these issues.
- **Exploration of Potential Solutions:** In this phase, the Living Lab engages stakeholders to explore various options for addressing the identified challenges. This is a collaborative process that includes brainstorming, knowledge sharing, and leveraging best practices from similar urban contexts.
- **Ideation and Conceptualisation of Solutions:** The solutions generated in the previous phase are further refined into concrete concepts. These are often supported by technical feasibility studies and stakeholder consultations to ensure that they are viable and contextually relevant.
- **Prototype Development:** Once solutions are conceptualised, they are developed into prototypes or pilot projects. These prototypes allow the Living Labs to test their ideas in a controlled, real-world environment, gathering feedback from stakeholders and measuring initial impacts.
- **Testing and Validation:** The prototypes are tested and validated through continuous stakeholder engagement. This phase ensures that the proposed solutions are, not only technically feasible, but also socially acceptable and sustainable over the long term.
- **Refinement and Iteration:** Based on the feedback from testing, the prototypes are refined and iterated. This phase emphasises the iterative nature of the Living Lab methodology, where solutions are continuously improved to better meet the needs of the stakeholders and adapt to new challenges.
- **Deployment Space:** After refinement, the solutions are ready for full deployment in the case study. This phase involves scaling the prototypes from small-scale pilots to case study-wide applications, ensuring that the solutions are integrated into broader urban planning and governance frameworks.

- **Implementation and Scale-up (PRO-CLIMATE Adaptation):** The final two phases—added specifically for the PRO-CLIMATE project—focus on implementing the solutions on a long-term basis and scaling them up to other cities or regions. This ensures that the innovations developed in the Living Labs can have a broader impact, contributing to climate resilience at a regional, national, or even international level.

2.4.4 Tools for Analysis

In addition to the methodological frameworks, several analytical tools were employed to support data collection and analysis. These tools included:

- **Survey Analytics Software:** The online questionnaires were analysed using survey analytics software (as MS Forms and MS Excel) to extract key insights, trends, and patterns. This allowed the project team to quickly identify common themes across the different Living Labs and focus on areas requiring further attention.
- **Stakeholder Mapping Tools:** To understand the complexity of stakeholder relationships within each Living Lab, stakeholder mapping tools were used to visualise networks of influence, identify key actors, and highlight potential areas of collaboration or conflict.

Combining these tools with the ENoLL and ULL approaches, the project ensured a robust and comprehensive analysis of the Living Labs' capacities and potential for fostering climate resilience.

2.5 Approach of the Contextualisation Process

The assessment of the six Living Labs (LLs) within the PRO-CLIMATE project revealed a diverse array of experiences, expertise, and challenges. These differences were rooted in the varying environmental, social, economic, and institutional contexts of the cases involved. The readiness of each LL to adopt and implement climate resilience strategies depended largely on their prior engagement in climate-related initiatives and stakeholder collaboration. Some cases displayed significant progress in climate action, while others required foundational support to effectively establish their LLs and engage stakeholders.

2.5.1 Key Findings from the Contextualisation Process

2.5.1.1 Variations in Environmental, Social, Economic, and Institutional Conditions

The cases participating in the PRO-CLIMATE project faced distinct environmental challenges, such as coastal erosion, flooding risks, and rising sea levels, which demanded tailored adaptation strategies (Thorne et al., 2007). Social conditions, including community awareness and involvement in climate action, varied considerably. Cases with high levels of social capital were able to engage stakeholders more effectively and leverage existing networks to accelerate co-creation processes. Conversely, cases with less organised communities needed additional efforts to build relationships and trust among stakeholders, which delayed the initial stages of LL establishment (ENoLL, 2018).

Economically, the capacity of LLs to secure resources for climate action was highly varied. Cases with greater access to financial and institutional backing, such as government or EU funding programs, were better positioned to implement large-scale climate adaptation projects. Cases with fewer resources required targeted capacity-building and technical assistance to support their LL activities. This disparity directly impacted each LL's ability to sustain long-term efforts and implement climate strategies (Bulkeley et al., 2016).

2.5.1.2 Varied Expectations for the Role of the Living Lab

The expectations of what each Living Lab could achieve also varied across cases. Some LLs viewed themselves as platforms for piloting small-scale climate solutions, such as nature-based interventions for coastal protection (Kokx, 2010). In these cases, the LLs focused on experimenting with specific innovations for potential scale-up. Other cases envisioned their LLs as long-term platforms for policy co-creation, bringing together a wide array of actors to influence broader urban planning and climate adaptation strategies.

The PRO-CLIMATE project team worked closely with each LL to ensure their expectations aligned with the project's objectives. If any case is focused on technical solutions, they will be encouraged to integrate social and institutional perspectives, while those prioritising policy co-creation were guided on how to incorporate technical innovations (Von Wirth et al., 2019).

2.5.1.3 Adaptive and Tailored Approaches

Given the diversity of the LLs, the PRO-CLIMATE project adopted an adaptive approach to implementing the Living Lab framework. Rather than enforcing a uniform solution, the project prioritised developing flexible, context-specific operational plans for each LL. These plans were co-created with stakeholders to ensure they reflected local priorities, capacities, and challenges.

For instance, in cases with less technical expertise, the project provided targeted training to build local capacity in areas, such as climate risk assessment and stakeholder engagement. In cases with financial constraints, operational plans included strategies for securing additional funding (ENoLL, 2018). The iterative nature of the framework allowed the plans to be updated continuously, reflecting new learnings and evolving local conditions.

2.5.1.4 Use of Data from Online Questionnaires and Bilateral Meetings

The data from online questionnaires and bilateral meetings played a critical role in shaping these tailored approaches. The questionnaires provided quantitative insights into each LL's maturity and preparedness, while the bilateral meetings offered qualitative discussions about local challenges and needs (Puerari et al., 2018).

For example, bilateral meetings revealed that some cases required extensive stakeholder engagement to ensure adequate community representation in LL activities. The project team responded by organising additional workshops and dialogues. In other cases, lacking technical expertise, operational plans included capacity-building activities, such as training sessions on climate modelling and resilience planning (Mastelic, 2019).

The assessment and contextualisation process underscored the need for a flexible, responsive approach in implementing the LL framework. Tailoring operational plans to the unique conditions of each Living Lab allowed for meaningful progress towards climate resilience, regardless of the starting point. Adopting adaptive strategies and using data-driven insights from questionnaires and meetings, the PRO-CLIMATE project ensured that all cases could benefit from the co-creation processes and achieve their climate adaptation goals.

3 Theoretical framework for Setting Up Living Labs

The Living Lab approach is an innovative concept which PRO-CLIMATE is based on. This section describes the Living Lab concept theory by presenting its main characteristics, methodology and framework.

3.1 Living Lab definition

We briefly introduced Living Lab in 2.4. Here we present a more thorough introduction of the Living Lab concept.

A Living Lab is defined as an open innovation ecosystem that operates in real-life environments, utilising iterative feedback throughout an innovation's lifecycle (known as the Living Lab integrative process). Its goal is to generate sustainable impact—whether economic, social, environmental, or regulatory—by acting as a mediator or orchestrator among citizens, research institutions, businesses, and government agencies. This collaboration occurs within the framework of the quadruple helix model (refer to section 3.3).

This concept comes from the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), the oldest and most established network of Living Labs. Since 2007, ENoLL has been defining and certifying Living Labs, with over 500 certified organisations to date.

There are four main types of Living Labs, classified based on open innovation networks (Leminen et al., 2012):

- **Utiliser-driven Living Labs** (also referred to as "Living Labs as a Service"): These labs provide companies with tools and methodologies to accelerate their innovation processes.
- **Enabler-driven Living Labs** (also known as "Urban and Rural Living Labs"): These labs turn cases or regions into sites for experimentation and co-creation, involving users actively and engaging multiple stakeholders.
- **Provider-driven Living Labs** (also called "Living Testbeds"): These focus on the development of new technologies and their societal acceptance.
- **User-driven Living Labs** (also known as "Research-Driven Living Labs"): These labs co-create solutions for specific user problems across various research topics, with the aim of creating lasting societal impact.

Most Living Labs incorporate elements from several of these types, but typically emphasise one as their primary focus. In the PRO-CLIMATE project, the six Living Labs are primarily categorised as enabler-driven, due to their focus on co-design, co-creation, and the integration of citizen science. Additionally, depending on the context of each case study, other open innovation network types are incorporated into these Living Labs.

3.2 Key characteristics of a Living Lab

3.2.1 Living Lab levels

A Living Lab operates on three interconnected levels: the macro, meso, and micro levels (Schuurman, 2015):

The **macro level** is centred on establishing a well-structured organisation, which involves coordinating and engaging various stakeholders based on a long-term vision and mission. It also requires a skilled Living Lab team with at least five different roles: Living Lab manager, project manager, panel manager, pilot manager, and human interaction specialist.

Building on this organisational foundation, the **meso level** focuses on developing Living Lab projects and methodologies that emphasise co-creation and active user participation in real-world environments.

At the **micro level**, these projects and methodologies are implemented through Living Lab (co-creation) activities using a multi-method approach, all conducted in real-life settings.

Figure 4 Living Lab levels

3.2.2 Living Lab building blocks

Each Living Lab is built on six key building blocks that span the three levels previously mentioned (macro, meso, and micro). Additionally, the roles of the Living Lab coordination team are clearly defined, as are the actors involved and their influence on innovation projects and processes. Together, these elements provide a comprehensive understanding of what needs to be considered when establishing a Living Lab. The six building blocks are (ENoLL, 2020):

- **Orchestration:** The Living Lab functions as an orchestrator within its ecosystem, fostering connections and partnerships with relevant stakeholders.
- **Co-creation:** Values within the Living Lab are co-created collaboratively and from the bottom up. This means that all relevant stakeholders are involved in shaping the innovation, which leads to higher adoption rates by the time the innovation process concludes.
- **Active User Involvement:** A Living Lab ensures that stakeholders actively participate in all relevant activities, continuously collecting and integrating their feedback throughout the entire innovation lifecycle.
- **Multi-Stakeholder Participation:** A holistic approach is taken, involving various stakeholders from government, academia, the private sector, and civil society, which corresponds to the quadruple helix model (see Section 3.3).
- **Real-Life Setting:** The Living Lab operates in the real-life environments of its end-users, embedding innovations directly into their day-to-day contexts rather than isolating them in test sites.
- **Multi-Method Approach:** Each activity within the Living Lab is driven by a specific problem. The methodology selected for each activity is tailored based on the expected outcomes and the involvement of relevant stakeholders.

These building blocks form the foundation for the effective functioning of a Living Lab, ensuring that it operates in a collaborative, real-world, and multi-disciplinary context.

Five key actors in Living Labs:

In relation to the six main building blocks of a Living Lab, five key actors have been identified, each playing a significant role in shaping the innovation processes (Leminen et al., 2012; Schuurman, 2015):

- **Utilisers:** These are the "customers" of the Living Lab who actively participate in co-creating innovations. Their involvement determines the scope and direction of the lab, significantly influencing the services offered and revenue streams at all levels (macro, meso, and micro).
- **Enablers:** Enablers provide the resources, often financial, necessary to sustain the Living Lab platform. Typical enablers include public innovation funds and university programs, operating primarily at the macro level. Other forms of enablers are less common.
- **Providers:** Providers offer the infrastructure or services used in Living Lab projects. They are especially dominant in test beds and technology-driven Living Labs, mainly functioning at the meso level.
- **Users:** These are the participants in the Living Lab activities, often forming a panel or community. Their involvement, though crucial at the micro level (where the innovation activities occur), does not always extend to the macro level in terms of governance.
- **Researchers:** Researchers are responsible for generating knowledge and guiding human interaction in the Living Lab. They focus on co-creation through action research and engage with stakeholders and users at all levels.

Living Lab coordination team roles:

To effectively manage and maintain the Living Lab's building blocks, it is essential to assign specific internal roles within the coordination team. While some of these roles can be combined, it's crucial that they are not all filled by a single person to ensure balanced management.

- **Living Lab Manager:** The primary leader of the Living Lab, responsible for overseeing day-to-day operations. The manager ensures the sustainability of the lab by developing projects that align with the lab's long-term strategy.
- **Project Manager:** This role involves managing individual Living Lab projects, including planning, procurement, and execution.
- **Pilot Manager:** The most technical member of the team, tasked with setting up, running, and scaling the technologies used in Living Lab projects.
- **Panel Manager:** The panel manager is responsible for managing communication, engagement, and interaction with both internal and external stakeholders, making this role the most people oriented.
- **Human Interaction Specialist:** The research-focused role, responsible for selecting, preparing, executing, and analysing co-creation methods and tools to ensure stakeholder and user collaboration is effective.

This structure ensures a well-rounded and coordinated effort to meet the needs of the different actors while keeping the Living Lab sustainable and adaptable to innovation processes.

3.2.3 Key points to build (successful) PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs

Since the study of Living Labs date back over a decade, there have been various Living Labs implemented, although highly concentrated in Europe (Ballon and Schuurman, 2015; Leminen et al., 2012; McPhee et al., 2017). Learning from the previous experience, we want to highlight some key points to build rather 'successful' Living Labs for PRO-CLIMATE.

- **Systems thinking:** according to Arnold and Wade's (Arnold and Wade, 2015) definition:

'Systems thinking is a set of synergistic analytic skills used to improve the capability of identifying and understanding systems, predicting their behaviours, and devising modifications to them in order to produce desired effects. These skills work together as a system.'

Figure 5 System Thinking Systemigram (Arnold and Wade, 2015)

Adopting a system thinking approach, the project seeks to understand the complex interactions and interdependencies among various components of the community system, including social, economic, cultural, and environmental factors, and how they influence community adaptation to climate change. One key aspect of PRO-CLIMATE’s approach is the emphasis it places on the importance of local, context-specific solutions by running six Living Labs across Europe. Applying systems thinking in PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs can help to better understand the complexities of the EU Adaptation Strategy and the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and ensure that policies and measures are tailored to local conditions, increasing their effectiveness and acceptance.

- **Stakeholder engagement:** one of the key points to build successful LLs is to design and follow a user engagement methodology that will enhance stakeholder engagement and commitment. Figure 6 gives a sample of proposed research methods for each step of the Living Lab integrative process.

	Empathise		Define	Ideate	Prototype	Test
	1	2	3	4	5	6
	Select a practice	Integrate stakeholders	Uncover Barriers	Co-design the intervention	Pilot the intervention	Evaluate performance
Desk research	X					
Workshops	X	X	X	X		
Quantitative analysis of determinants of consumption	X				X	X
Clustering methods	X	X				
Expert interviews/Delphi Method	X		X			
Ethnographic observations	X		X		X	
Qualitative interviews	X	X	X			
Persona (Tool)		X				
Pain & Gain (Tool)			X			
Co-design workshop				X		
Rapid prototyping				X		
Eye tracking					X	
Quasi-experiment					X	
Econometrics						X
Surveys	X				X	X

Figure 6 Sample of proposed research methods for each step of the Living Lab integrative process. (Source: SCORE project public deliverable)

- **Capacity building:** one of the main PRO-CLIMATE objectives is to facilitate systemic transformation through behaviour change. Capacity building is a crucial element of

successful organisational change. It involves developing the skills, knowledge, culture, and mindset necessary to effectively navigate change and adapt to evolving circumstances. This will involve empowering community members with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to adapt to climate change, including climate literacy, risk assessment, and adaptive decision-making. Tapping this into building PRO-CLIMATE LLs is essential to reach the project targets.

3.3 Living Lab approach

The concept of Living Labs as a research approach is to enhance engagement and participation of end-users in the development and implementation process of innovations (Zipfel et al., 2022). The key stakeholder's engagement methods are presented in this section.

3.3.1 Application of the quadruple helix model

As mentioned in 3.2.3, active stakeholder engagement is the key to implement the LLs. Achieving this goal, we adopted the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) to identify key stakeholders in LLs.

The Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) is an evolution of the Triple Helix Model (THM), first introduced by Carayannis and Campbell in 2009, to include civil society and highlight its involvement in the creation of knowledge and innovation. Both models emphasise structures where innovation is driven by co-creation among actors, with knowledge flowing freely without barriers (García-Terán and Skoglund, 2019).

Cavallini and the colleagues (Committee of the Regions. Commission for Social Policy, Education, Employment, Research and Culture. et al., 2016) defined the THM and OHM as:

'grounded on the idea that innovation is the outcome of an interactive process involving different spheres of actors, each contributing according to its 'institutional' function in society'

The QHM identifies four key categories (Committee of the Regions. Commission for Social Policy, Education, Employment, Research and Culture. et al., 2016; Finquelievich, 2017):

- **Academia and Universities:** Historically essential for knowledge production, this sector has recently become a significant contributor to innovation, due to the increasing importance of knowledge in innovation development. Academia now plays a key role in driving both economic and cultural growth.
- **Industry and Business:** Often referred to as the commercial market or economic sector, industry is a leading force in technological and organisational innovation. It generates, produces, and distributes products and services, often working either independently or in partnership with other stakeholders to create innovations.
- **Government and Public Sector:** Innovation in the government sphere focuses on new ideas that create societal value, typically through policies, strategies, and initiatives. This sector's role is to support both industry and academia in applying knowledge to promote development.
- **Civil Society:** Representing citizens and end-users, civil society contributes insights into their needs, experiences, and expectations. As they are directly impacted by changes in the urban environment, their feedback provides crucial, first-hand information about the issues under study. Incorporating civil society into the THM, transforming it into the QHM, the focus of innovation shifts from purely technical advancements to social innovation as well.

The identification of the key stakeholders in PRO-CLIMATE based on this QHM is introduced in session 3.3.2.

3.3.2 Identification of stakeholder needs and priorities

In the PRO-CLIMATE project, the identification of stakeholder needs and priorities is important to the successful establishment of the Living Labs (LLs) in the cases of Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Bergen (Norway), Badajoz (Spain), Zakynthos (Greece), and Gdansk (Poland). These Living Labs are designed to address climate resilience challenges specific to each case study's

environmental, social, and economic context. To achieve this, the project utilises a variety of participatory techniques, combined with the **Quadruple Helix model**, to engage stakeholders from four key sectors: academia, industry, government, and civil society.

3.3.2.1 Techniques for Identifying Stakeholder Needs

- 1) **Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis:** Stakeholder mapping is one of the first steps in identifying the needs and priorities of different actors involved in each Living Lab. This technique involves:
 - Identifying key stakeholders: Actors from the public sector, private companies, research institutions, and local communities are mapped according to their influence and interest in climate resilience initiatives.
 - Categorising stakeholders by role: Stakeholders are classified according to their role in the project, such as decision-makers, technical experts, or local advocates. This helps in understanding their expectations and the level of support they can provide (Puerari et al., 2018).
 - Assessing stakeholder influence and interest: This matrix allows the project team to focus on highly influential stakeholders who have a vested interest in the success of climate adaptation strategies, ensuring their needs are prioritised in the decision-making process (Schuurman et al., 2017).
- 2) **Workshops and Co-Creation Sessions:** Co-creation workshops are central to understanding stakeholder needs. These sessions involve interactive and participatory techniques that allow stakeholders to express their concerns and collaboratively brainstorm solutions. The design thinking approach, as suggested by Brown and Katz (2011), is used to foster creative problem-solving during these workshops, where stakeholders can:
 - Discuss and validate climate-related challenges specific to their local context.
 - Engage in scenario planning to explore potential impacts of climate change and how different strategies can address these challenges (ENoLL, 2018).
 - Prioritise key actions and innovations, ensuring that proposed solutions are aligned with the needs of the community and other local stakeholders.
- 3) **Bilateral Meetings:** Bilateral meetings between the PRO-CLIMATE project team and individual stakeholder groups are another technique used to gain a deeper understanding of specific needs. These meetings are especially useful for addressing more nuanced concerns that may not emerge in group workshops. Engaging with local governments, business leaders, and community representatives in focused discussions, the project team can ensure that the Living Labs' strategies remain flexible and responsive to local dynamics (Arnkil et al., 2019).
- 4) **Online Surveys:** Online questionnaires, distributed to stakeholders during the project's early stages, provide a structured way to gather input on priorities. The survey design incorporates questions related to:
 - Stakeholder objectives for climate resilience.
 - Local challenges and opportunities for adaptation.
 - Available resources and potential barriers to implementation (Tomaszewski, 2020). This technique ensures broad participation, enabling the project to gather quantitative data that complements the qualitative insights gained through workshops and meetings.

3.3.2.2 The Quadruple Helix Model in the PRO-CLIMATE Project

The PRO-CLIMATE project adopts the Quadruple Helix model as a guiding framework for stakeholder engagement. This model recognizes the interdependence of four sectors—academia,

industry, government, and civil society—in driving innovation and addressing complex societal challenges like climate change (Arnkil et al., 2010).

- **Academia:** Research institutions, such as universities and environmental research centres, play a critical role in providing scientific knowledge and technical expertise. In cases like Leipzig and Bergen, where local universities have strong environmental science programs, these institutions help assess climate risks, model future scenarios, and develop data-driven solutions for resilience (Schuurman et al., 2017). Their role is to inform the co-creation process by integrating evidence-based practices into climate adaptation strategies.
- **Industry:** In the PRO-CLIMATE project, industry stakeholders—particularly in coastal management, renewable energy, and infrastructure—are essential for scaling innovations. For example, in Sligo and Gdansk, companies involved in green technologies contribute by offering solutions for sustainable urban development and coastal defence mechanisms. The involvement of private sector actors ensures that the innovations developed within the Living Labs are financially viable and can be implemented on a larger scale (Leminen et al., 2012).
- **Government:** Local governments in the six cases are pivotal for the institutionalisation of the Living Labs. As key decision-makers, they provide regulatory support and facilitate the implementation of climate adaptation policies. In Badajoz and Zakynthos, for instance, government agencies are actively involved in the operation of the Living Labs. The involvement of the local governments could bring tangible benefits for the Labs, such as potential access to public funding and resources, which are critical for sustaining the Labs beyond the project's timeline (Mastelic, 2019).
- **Civil Society:** Civil society, including local communities, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and citizen groups, brings the voice of the public into the co-creation process. In cases like Badajoz, where local communities face significant environmental challenges, citizen involvement ensures that the solutions developed are relevant to the everyday experiences of those most affected by climate risks. Engaging with civil society, the PRO-CLIMATE project fosters community ownership of the solutions, making them more likely to be adopted and maintained (Puerari et al., 2018).

3.3.2.3 Prioritising Stakeholder Needs

The use of the Quadruple Helix model enables the PRO-CLIMATE project to balance the needs and priorities of different stakeholders effectively. Through continuous dialogue and feedback loops facilitated by the techniques described above, each case study's Living Lab can adapt to evolving priorities. In Sligo, for example, the focus may be on developing green infrastructure to protect coastal areas, while in Leipzig, the priority might shift to financial efficient urban mitigation strategies. The Quadruple Helix model ensures that these varied priorities are addressed through a collaborative, multi-stakeholder approach that leverages the strengths of all sectors involved.

Prioritizing stakeholder needs in a structured manner, the PRO-CLIMATE project ensures that the Living Labs remain dynamic and adaptable to local contexts, with each Lab uniquely positioned to tackle the specific climate resilience challenges faced by its local context.

3.3.3 Strategies for citizen engagement

Citizen engagement is an important element of the PRO-CLIMATE project, particularly in the establishment and operation of its Living Labs (LLs) in Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Bergen (Norway), Badajoz (Spain), Zakynthos (Greece), and Gdansk (Poland). These LLs aim to build climate resilience through collaborative, community-driven processes. Involving citizens at every stage—from identifying problems to co-creating and implementing solutions—the project ensures that local perspectives and knowledge are integral to developing sustainable climate adaptation strategies. Effective citizen engagement enhances both the relevance and legitimacy of the solutions developed while fostering long-term community ownership and participation (Compagnucci, 2020).

The engagement strategies outlined here draw from participatory design, social innovation practices, and the Quadruple Helix model, integrating input from citizens alongside academia, industry, and

government stakeholders. The structured tasks within the PRO-CLIMATE project ensure that these strategies are systematically implemented and adapted to each case study's unique social, cultural, and environmental context.

a. Participatory Workshops and Co-Creation Sessions

A core component of the PRO-CLIMATE project's citizen engagement approach is the use of participatory workshops and co-creation sessions. These workshops are designed to actively involve citizens, local stakeholders, and experts in identifying local climate challenges and generating solutions. Based on the principles of design thinking (Brown & Katz, 2011), these sessions allow citizens to engage deeply with climate resilience efforts and provide a platform for their insights to shape the Living Lab's activities.

The workshops focus on several key activities:

- **Scenario Planning:** Citizens collaborate with experts to envision future climate impacts on their communities and explore potential adaptation strategies. This method helps participants evaluate the effectiveness of different solutions and promotes critical thinking about the challenges they face.
- **Stakeholder Mapping:** Participants identify key local actors—ranging from government entities and businesses to community organisations—who should be involved in the resilience efforts. This process ensures a comprehensive understanding of local dynamics and fosters collaboration across sectors.
- **Solution Prototyping:** Citizens engage in the co-design and testing of nature-based or other climate adaptation solutions. These prototypes will be refined and potentially implemented within the Living Labs, translating community input into concrete actions.

These workshops are integral to Task 2.2, which focuses on developing Pilot Operational Plans (POP) for each Living Lab. The workshops will be organised in each case study to prepare these plans, which outline the specific steps and activities for the Living Labs.

b. Citizen Science Initiatives

Citizen science is a key engagement strategy within the PRO-CLIMATE project, designed to involve residents in environmental monitoring and data collection activities. Contributing to scientific research, citizens play an active role in identifying and addressing the specific climate challenges their cases face.

This participatory approach empowers communities to contribute valuable data while fostering a deeper understanding of climate resilience issues. Integrating citizen science, the PRO-CLIMATE project ensures that local knowledge is leveraged in developing effective, context-specific solutions.

c. Public Hearings and Deliberative Forums

Public hearings and deliberative forums will provide formal spaces for citizens, experts, and policymakers to discuss proposed climate adaptation strategies. These events foster transparent dialogue and allow citizens to influence policy decisions directly.

- **Public Hearings:** Local governments will organise these hearings in cases like Badajoz and Gdansk, where citizens can provide input on regulatory measures and climate policies.
- **Deliberative Forums:** These forums will enable deeper discussions between citizens and decision-makers, ensuring that policy choices reflect community priorities and concerns.

These public discussions will enhance the democratic governance of climate adaptation strategies, empowering citizens to shape the policies that impact their lives.

d. Educational Campaigns and Outreach

To sustain long-term engagement, the PRO-CLIMATE project will implement educational campaigns aimed at raising awareness about climate resilience and encouraging active participation in Living

Lab activities. These campaigns will target schools, universities, and community groups to foster a culture of environmental stewardship.

Building climate literacy across all age groups, the PRO-CLIMATE project ensures that engagement is sustained beyond the immediate project timeline.

Tailoring Engagement Strategies to Local Contexts

While the engagement strategies follow a consistent framework across the six cases, they are carefully adapted to reflect the specific needs of each location.

This tailored approach ensures that the PRO-CLIMATE project's engagement strategies are relevant to the unique environmental and social challenges of each case study.

The PRO-CLIMATE project's citizen engagement strategies are designed to ensure that local communities are integral to the development and implementation of climate resilience strategies. Employing a variety of participatory methods—including workshops, citizen science, digital platforms, and public hearings—the project ensures that the Living Labs in Sligo, Leipzig, Bergen, Badajoz, Zakynthos, and Gdansk are responsive to the specific needs of their citizens. Ultimately, these strategies foster community ownership and long-term commitment, empowering citizens to play an active role in building climate resilience.

3.3.4 Principles of co-design and co-creation

Co-creation is understood as a process that, based on the identified needs, aims to develop results that involve knowledge flows and absorptive capacities from all actors involved across the entire economic and social environment, referred to the addressed needs (“Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter - European Commission,” 2023).

Co-design is a specific instance of the broader concept of co-creation and refers to the creativity of designers and people not trained in design working together in the design development process.

Both co-design and co-creation are essential process through the Living Lab approach. In PRO-CLIMATE case studies, co-creation is the results of the process that different ideas, practices, norms, knowledge, and expertise shared, exchanged, and evolved to build a consistent and sustainable LL, while the solutions needed to adapt to the climate challenges each case study is facing will be co-designed through the LLs.

3.3.5 Community-based social marketing approaches

Community-Based Social Marketing (CBSM) methods, grounded in social psychology, focus on encouraging sustainable behaviour change through direct interaction with individuals and communities (McKenzie-Mohr, 2011). These methods aim to identify barriers to desired behaviours and implement targeted interventions to facilitate change (McKenzie-Mohr, 2000). The CBSM approach follows four key steps:

- 1) Uncovering barriers and selecting behaviours: Identify both internal and external obstacles that hinder the adoption of specific behaviours.
- 2) Designing strategies: Develop a social marketing strategy that addresses these barriers to promote the desired behaviour change.
- 3) Piloting: Before broad implementation, the strategy should be tested on a smaller scale to ensure its effectiveness.
- 4) Evaluation: The evaluation process in CBSM focuses on directly assessing the behaviour or its outcomes to measure success.

3.4 Framework to build PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs

Considering the building blocks, principles and stakeholders of LLs, combining with systems thinking process, an initial PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab framework is developed and presented in this deliverable. This framework will be updated in future versions based on knowledge and experience gained from the implementation of PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs. Figure 7 shows an overview of the

framework which consists of six stages. Each stage is introduced more in details in the following texts.

Figure 7 PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab Framework

3.4.1 Contextualization

3.4.1.1 Baseline Analysis

Conduct a thorough baseline analysis to gather and evaluate data on current environmental, social, and economic conditions within the Living Lab context. This analysis serves as a foundation for understanding existing challenges, resource availability, community dynamics, and to identify one/two local climate issues. It will guide future Living Lab activities.

This step also includes the scoping of the needed roles and responsibilities within the governance of PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs and the coordination team. The change agents within the Living Labs should also be defined in this step.

3.4.1.2 Stakeholder Identification

This step needs to identify all relevant stakeholders. Mapping out stakeholders from the quadruple helix model and understanding their interests and influences is essential for fostering collaboration and ensuring diverse input in the Living Lab process.

3.4.1.3 Focal Action Situation Identification

This step needs to identify a specific context or situation where collective action, and decision-making processes are particularly relevant to climate change and can have a significant impact on local livelihoods. It could be a specific activity, a conflict situation, or a governance structure related to achieving systemic transformations towards climate resilience. This situation should reflect the priorities identified during the baseline analysis and engage stakeholders in meaningful dialogue about the challenges and opportunities present.

3.4.2 Co-creation

This stage equips participants with the resources needed to create prototypes and empowers users with innovative solutions. While numerous ideas emerge during the ideation process, the optimal solution is identified through testing and feedback. Techniques that can be employed during this phase include brainstorming, mind-mapping, and sketching, among others.

The stages of co-creation, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation is an iterative process.

3.4.2.1 Co-design - Ideation

In this step, a variety of ideas are generated, and concepts and outcomes are explored in depth.

3.4.2.2 Prototype

Create prototypes based on the co-designed ideas, allowing stakeholders to visualise potential interventions. Prototyping serves as a tangible representation of concepts, fostering iterative feedback and refinement before full-scale implementation.

3.4.2.3 Test

Conduct testing of the prototypes in real-world settings to evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness. Gather feedback from stakeholders to make necessary adjustments, ensuring that the final implementations are responsive to community needs and contexts.

3.4.3 Implementation

During the implementation stage, the co-created solution will be integrated into a practical operational environment together with all actions from different Living Lab levels.

3.4.3.1 Integrating Good Governance Measures

Establish good governance measures to ensure transparency, accountability, and active stakeholder engagement throughout the implementation process. Effective governance is critical for maintaining trust, fostering inclusive participation, and addressing potential conflicts.

3.4.3.2 Capacity Building

Implement capacity-building initiatives to empower stakeholders with the necessary skills and knowledge for active participation. This may include training workshops, educational programs, and resource-sharing activities.

3.4.4 Monitoring & Evaluation

3.4.4.1 Understanding Dynamic Behaviour

Monitor the dynamic behaviours within the system throughout the implementation phase. This involves analysing how various factors interact and evolve, which is essential for adapting strategies to changing conditions and stakeholder feedback. Understanding these dynamics helps in making informed decisions and optimising interventions.

3.4.4.2 Identifying Potential Social Tipping Points

Identify and monitor potential social tipping points that could catalyse larger systemic changes. Recognising these points can provide insights into opportunities for scaling successful initiatives and engaging the broader community in climate action.

The aim in PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab is to understand the dynamics of socio-ecological systems driving climate change and to pinpoint strategic leverage points where policy actions can trigger positive feedback loops, leading to accelerated change.

3.4.5 Up-scaling

3.4.5.1 Policy Recommendation

This step aims to provide concrete recommendations of operational nature to accelerate systemic change in the regions and communities that served as case studies. These recommendations aim to inform local, regional, and national policies that support sustainable climate actions and integrate successful practices into formal governance frameworks.

3.4.5.2 Decision-making Support Tool

This step focuses on designing a tool that can empower policy makers to identify and leverage critical social tipping points in their specific policy domains and to rapidly appraise the impact of interventions on the system.

3.4.6 Living Lab Sustainability Plan

Formulate a sustainability plan to ensure the long-term viability of the Living Lab beyond initial funding and project timelines. This plan should include strategies for ongoing stakeholder engagement, resource mobilisation, and integration into existing governance structures, ensuring that the efforts initiated within the Living Lab continue to thrive.

4 PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs Contextualization

As introduced in the methodology (section 2), we followed the baseline questionnaire structure (shown in figure 8) to collect the baseline data through online questionnaires, bilateral meetings, and workshops from all the Living Labs. Then following the six key LL building blocks introduced in 3.2.2 and the 'ENoLL Approach' (Overdiek and Genova, 2021), we evaluate the six PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs' maturity.

Figure 8 Baseline data collection structure

4.1 Overall baseline assessment results

Table 1 shows the six Living Labs' knowledge levels based on the baseline questionnaire structure.

Table 1 PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs Baseline Knowledge Levels

Structure	Badajoz, Spain	Bergen, Norway	Gdańsk, Poland	Leipzig, Germany	Sligo, Ireland	Zakynthos, Greece
LL Experience	1	3	4	1	4	4
LL Objectives	4	5	5	3	5	5
LL Methodology-Scoping and Selecting a Practice	3	5	5	3	5	4
LL Methodology-Integrate Stakeholders	2	4	4	3	4	4
LL Methodology-Uncover Barriers	3	4	4	4	4	3
LL Methodology-Co-design Plan	2	3	3	1	3	4
LL Methodology-Pilot an Intervention	1	2	2	1	4	4

D2.1 Baseline Assessment and Knowledge Gathering for the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs

LL Methodology-Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment	1	2	2	1	2	3
LL Methodology-Demonstrate the System	1	2	3	1	3	4
LL Methodology-Scaling-up the Solution	1	1	2	1	2	4
LL Management	1	1	3	1	4	3
Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability	2	2	3	2	3	3

Note: 1-no knowledge; 2-limited knowledge; 3-some knowledge; 4-extensive knowledge; 5-excellent knowledge.

In general, all the cases perform well in setting LL Objectives and scoping and selecting a practice, which are essential at the beginning stage to set up the Living Labs. However, a mixed level of knowledge across the Living Lab (LL) methodologies. Most cases, particularly Sligo, Zakynthos, Bergen, and Gdansk, show strong performance in the methods used in the early stages of Living Labs for scoping and selecting a solution, stakeholder integration, and co-designing plans, while there is a clear gap in knowledge and expertise when it comes to more practical and operational aspects, such as demonstrating systems, evaluating performance, and scaling-up solutions, where most cases score lower. These areas reflect a common challenge across the board, indicating that while cases may be strong in planning and managing LL activities, they struggle with implementation and long-term sustainability. Additionally, the understanding of challenges, risks, and sustainability can be enhanced, with most cases showing room for improvement in addressing these long-term considerations.

Table 2 shows the overall scores of each PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab based on the data collected from the surveys. This information includes the baseline settings of the LLs but does not capture current or future performance of the PRO-CLIMATE LLs.

Table 2 PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab Organisational Maturity

ENoLL Attribute	Sligo (Ireland)	Badajoz (Spain)	Leipzig (Germany)	Bergen (Norway)	Gdańsk (Poland)	Zakynthos (Greece)
Active user involvement	4.00	3.40	3.40	4.20	5.00	5.00
Co-creation	3.10	1.71	1.71	1.29	3.71	4.14
Multi-method approach	2.78	2.00	0.67	2.33	3.44	4.78
Multi-stakeholder participation	3.80	3.80	2.80	3.40	4.40	4.30
Orchestration	3.30	1.38	1.19	1.94	1.88	3.38
Real-life setting	3.71	3.71	3.43	3.00	3.43	2.86
Overall score	3.46	2.67	2.20	2.69	3.64	4.08

Note: the higher scores means better performance.

Based on the results, Zakynthos (Greece), Gdańsk (Poland) and Sligo (Ireland) show relatively high in Living Lab maturity, although it is noted that these are at different stages of their establishment (e.g., Zakynthos is in the process of setting up). They consistently perform well across most attributes, particularly in Active User Involvement, Multi-method Approaches, and Multi-stakeholder Participation. These regions have well-established innovation ecosystems to involve users, utilise diverse approaches, and engage various stakeholders effectively. In contrast, Leipzig (Germany), Badajoz (Spain) and Bergen (Norway) need more support in improving their maturity to set up the Living Labs. They struggle with several key attributes, particularly in Orchestration, Co-creation, and

Multi-method Approaches, indicating that their innovation processes lack strong coordination and diversity of methods.

For each of the Living Lab building blocks, the key results are shown as follows:

- Active user involvement: Gdansk and Zakynthos have more established frameworks to include users in decision-making or co-creation processes. In contrast, Badajoz and Leipzig might benefit from enhanced strategies to boost user involvement.
- Co-creation: Badajoz, Leipzig, and Bergen need to develop better co-creation practices, such as participatory workshops, collaborative design approaches, to foster active stakeholder engagement.
- Multi-method approach: Most of the Living Labs perform low in this attribute, especially Leipzig shows the weakest point. A knowledge sharing among the Living Labs can help the lower score one gain practical experience from the others, such as Zakynthos and Gdansk.
- Multi-stakeholder participation: All the Living Labs perform generally good in this attribute. Gdansk and Zakynthos emphasise the inclusion of multiple stakeholders in their initiatives, while Leipzig could result in more robust, well-rounded outcomes by expanding participation from different sectors.
- Orchestration: Most of the Living Labs show low status in orchestration. This can be enhanced by further developing stakeholder engagement strategies and POPs for each Living Lab.
- Real-life setting: Sligo and Badajoz show the highest integration of real-life settings, while Zakynthos scores relatively low, suggesting more efforts are needed to translate skills and knowledge into practical, real-world applications.

4.2 Stakeholders Identification results

Stakeholder identification is an important process in the PRO-CLIMATE project aimed at ensuring the success of the Living Labs (LLs) being established across various cases. The goal of stakeholder identification is to map key actors who have influence, interest, and the capacity to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of climate resilience strategies. This chapter provides an overview of the stakeholders identified in the six cases, the methodologies applied for their classification, and their roles in contributing to the Living Lab framework.

The stakeholder identification process was conducted following a structured methodology aligned with the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) framework and the Quadruple Helix model, both of which emphasise the importance of involving multi-sector stakeholders (fig. 9). These methodologies promote open innovation, user-centric approaches, and the integration of knowledge from academia, industry, government, and civil society.

Figure 9 highlights the diverse involvement of stakeholders across the Living Labs, with Badajoz showing strong industry participation, while other labs, like Sligo and Leipzig, demonstrate a more balanced representation across the quadruple helix sectors. Public ownership dominates most LLs, particularly in Badajoz, Gdansk, and Sligo, with significant contributions from NGOs and community groups in select cases.

Ownership+Quadruple Helix

Figure 9 Stakeholders' identification process using Quadruple Helix Model

Key steps in the stakeholder identification process include:

- Mapping and Categorisation:** Stakeholders were categorised by their sector, involvement status, and level of influence or interest in the project.
- Assessment of Engagement Strategies:** Each stakeholder's role and influence were analysed to determine the optimal engagement strategy, ensuring their involvement was effective and aligned with the Living Lab's goals.
- RACI (Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed) Matrix:** The RACI matrix helped define the roles and responsibilities of each stakeholder in relation to the PRO-CLIMATE project's key tasks.

4.2.1 Overview of Identified Stakeholders

Based on the analysis of the stakeholder identification document, the following sectors were represented (Fig. 10):

- **Academia:** Academia provides essential scientific research and knowledge, contributing to evidence-based decision-making for climate resilience.
- **Government and Public Sector:** These stakeholders have high levels of power and interest in the project, particularly in policy alignment, regulatory frameworks, and urban planning.
- **Civil Society:** Although civil society stakeholders were not explicitly identified in the initial phase, there is a clear opportunity to engage local community groups and NGOs in the next stages. Their involvement will ensure that the solutions developed within the Living Labs reflect the concerns and needs of residents.
- **Industry:** At this stage, the involvement of industry stakeholders is limited. However, their future engagement will be essential, particularly in areas, such as urban infrastructure and green technologies, to support the scalability and financial viability of the project's solutions.

From Figure 10, we can see that Badajoz has the largest concentration of stakeholders, particularly from Industry (38), followed by significant participation from Civil Society and Government/Public Sector. Other labs, such as Sligo, Leipzig, and Gdansk, show more balanced stakeholder engagement across all four sectors, with no single group being overwhelmingly dominant.

Figure 10 Stakeholders' analysis based on quadruple helix model

Analysis Techniques Applied

- a) **Power-Interest Matrix:** Stakeholders were categorised based on their level of power and interest in the PRO-CLIMATE project:
- High Power, High Interest
 - Medium Power, Medium Interest

At this stage of the project, we are employing the Power/Interest matrix as a tool to categorise and better understand the stakeholders identified from the Living Labs (LLs). The matrix allows us to evaluate stakeholders based on two key dimensions:

1. Power, which is the ability of a stakeholder to influence or impact the project.
2. Interest, which is the degree to which a stakeholder is invested in or affected by the project's outcomes.

This includes stakeholders who are highly interested and aligned with the project, as well as those with low interest or conflicting priorities. The matrix not only helps us identify key stakeholders, who are already interested and supportive, but also highlights those with lower interest or even conflicting positions. Understanding these groups is crucial for designing targeted engagement strategies to address their concerns or mitigate potential conflicts. Our primary goal is to build a comprehensive understanding of the stakeholder landscape as identified by the LLs.

Based on the results of the survey and bilateral meetings, Figure 11 presents a Power-Interest Matrix for all six Living Labs from the PRO-CLIMATE project, mapping stakeholders from the quadruple helix model (Academia, Civil Society, Government/Public Sector, Industry), according to their levels of power (high or medium) and interest. We can observe from this figure that in Badajoz and Zakynthos, Government/Public Sector actors hold high power and low interest, while in other Living Labs like Bergen and Leipzig, stakeholders are more evenly distributed between high and medium levels of power and interest across different sectors. This suggests varied levels of influence and engagement from different sectors depending on the location.

Figure 11 Stakeholders' Power-Interest matrix

- b) **Stakeholder Mapping by Sector:** This analysis revealed that the majority of stakeholders identified belong to the government sector, followed by academia. There is an evident need to increase the representation of industry and civil society actors to ensure a more balanced collaboration that encompasses diverse perspectives and expertise.

For the PRO-CLIMATE project, Figure 12 presents an analysis of stakeholder distribution across various sectors, prepared for all six Living Labs. It highlights significant involvement from sector bodies/authorities in Badajoz, while other labs, such as Sligo and Gdansk, demonstrate more balanced participation across sectors like civic groups, education, and environment.

Figure 12 Stakeholders' analysis based on sector mapping

c) **RACI Matrix:** The RACI matrix was used to clarify roles for key tasks in the project. They are:

- Responsible (R)
- Accountable (A)
- Consulted (C)
- Informed (I)

(RACI matrix analysis will be added later)

Key Insights and Recommendations

- **Governmental Involvement:** The active involvement of municipal stakeholders is a significant strength for the project. Their influence in local governance and policymaking will facilitate the successful integration of the Living Labs' climate resilience strategies into broader urban planning frameworks.
- **Gaps in Industry and Civil Society Engagement:** The absence of identified industry stakeholders and limited civil society involvement highlight areas where future efforts should focus. Engaging these sectors will be critical for ensuring the feasibility, scalability, and social inclusiveness of the project's outcomes.
- **Tailored Engagement Strategies:** Different stakeholders require distinct engagement approaches. High-power stakeholders should be continuously involved in decision-making, while stakeholders with lower interest, such as potential industry partners, can be brought in at specific stages to provide technical support or co-investment.

The stakeholder identification process for the PRO-CLIMATE project has provided a comprehensive overview of the key actors involved in the Living Lab framework, as highlighted in Figure 13. Utilising methodologies like the ENoLL approach and the Quadruple Helix model, the project has ensured a structured, inclusive process for engaging stakeholders across different sectors. Moving forward, efforts should focus on broadening the involvement of civil society and industry actors to enhance the project's impact and sustainability. Through continuous stakeholder engagement, the Living Labs will be well-positioned to co-create innovative solutions that address the case study's unique climate resilience challenges.

Figure 13 presents an analysis of stakeholder involvement status, prepared for all six Living Labs in the PRO-CLIMATE project, distinguishing between those already involved and those still to be invited. Badajoz has the highest number of stakeholders to be invited at the local scale, with 32 yet to be engaged. Other Living Labs, such as Sligo and Zakynthos, show a more balanced distribution of stakeholders between different levels of governance (local, regional, national), with fewer pending invitations.

Sector&Involvement

Figure 13 Stakeholders' Involvement

4.3 Key insights and patterns observed for each Living Lab

This section presents the key assessment results of each PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab based on the baseline questionnaire structure (LL Experience, LL Objectives, LL Methodology, LL Management, and Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability).

4.3.1 Badajoz, Spain

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: No knowledge or experience.
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Badajoz views Living Labs as collaborative environments focused on public policy improvements, but the lack of practical experience limits their current implementation.
- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Improving public policies and facilitating sustainable behaviour change.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: Developing governance strategies that combine social good with environmental agendas.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Developing a climate change adaptation action plan.
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Initiating the integration of stakeholders in the decision-making process.
- LL Methodology:
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: The focus is on identifying policy-related practices that can be improved through Living Lab processes. They are in the initial stages of scoping.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: Stakeholder integration is still in development.
 - ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Main barriers include limited awareness of climate change and the local economy highly dependent on agriculture.
 - ⇒ Co-design Plan: Limited knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ The co-design process focuses on creating frameworks for policy improvement through collaborative discussions.
 - ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: No knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Pilot interventions are planned but not yet implemented.
 - ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: No knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Draft evaluation plan is being developed but need to be reviewed by the actual case study of the Living Lab.
 - ⇒ Demonstrate the System: No knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ System demonstrations are planned but have not yet been fully developed.
 - ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: No knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Plans for scaling are not yet in place, but will focus on expanding stakeholder engagement processes.
- LL Management: Limited information, but it's clear they are in the process of setting up management structures to facilitate stakeholder engagement.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: They face a major challenge in developing a stakeholder engagement strategy. This is crucial for ensuring that future initiatives are inclusive and effective.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Long-term sustainability depends on integrating with local policies and strategies, with diverse funding sources.

4.3.2 Bergen, Norway

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: Some knowledge and experience.
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Bergen has engaged in a co-creation and co-design process for land-use decision-making. This indicates a moderate level of involvement, particularly in environmental and urban planning domains.

- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Sustainable urban land planning.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: Upscaling the solutions developed through the Living Lab.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Implementing and refining co-creation methods for stakeholder participation in urban planning.
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Identifying and involving stakeholders in land-use processes.
- LL Methodology
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: Bergen has selected land-use planning as the practice for their Living Lab, focusing on sustainable urbanisation.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: Stakeholders have been well-defined.
 - ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Bergen faces barriers related to conflicting interests among land-use stakeholders, which complicates decision-making.
 - ⇒ Co-design Plan: Some knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Co-design activities involve stakeholders working together to develop land-use policies that reflect collective input.
 - ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: Limited knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Pilot interventions in Bergen involve testing new urban land planning strategy and tracking their impact.
 - ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: Limited knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ Performance evaluations focus on the use of Bergen urban land planning strategy, assessing the citizen engagement and whether the strategy achieve sustainability goals.
 - ⇒ Demonstrate the System: Limited knowledge & experience.
 - ⇒ No plans currently exist on this.
 - ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: No knowledge & experience.
No plans currently exist on this.
- LL Management: No concrete management plan.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: Understanding what Living Lab is and the continuation of Bergen Living Lab after the project ends.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Long-term sustainability depends on running the Living Lab effectively and efficiently, active stakeholder participation, and a fix Living Lab manager role.

4.3.3 Gdansk, Poland

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: Extensive knowledge and experience.
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Gdansk perceives Living Labs as spaces for active citizen and technology collaboration. Its Living Lab has extensive engagement with the EU-funded SCORE project.
- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Mitigating the effects of severe rainfall in Gdansk through adaptation to behavioural change through systematic transformation and good governance structures.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: Developing Living Lab sustainability plan.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Producing knowledge and data that will create systematic transformation through effective governance.
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Following the PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab framework to increase the Living Lab maturity.
- LL Methodology:
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: Scoping has focused on torrential rains - pluvial flooding (inland flooding) from waterways (e.g., rivers, streams within the city's borders reach maximal water retention capacity) occurring during the months June-August.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: A wide range of stakeholders is integrated.

- ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Gdansk faces challenges in scaling technology solutions due to funding and regulatory barriers.
- ⇒ Co-design plan: Some knowledge & experience.
- ⇒ Co-designing solutions in collaboration with local stakeholders and guided by EU policies.
- ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: Limited knowledge & experience.
- ⇒ Gdansk is piloting technology solutions aimed at improving local governance and public participation.
- ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: Limited knowledge & experience. Regular evaluations are conducted as part of the SCORE project.
- ⇒ Demonstrate the System: Some knowledge & experience.
- ⇒ Gdansk demonstrates the use of technology in improving public services and governance.
- ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: Limited knowledge & experience.
- ⇒ Gdansk would like to scale up innovative solutions/activities/outcomes but it needs to be supported by good governance.
- LL Management: Gdansk has some management strategies including inviting the key stakeholders-environmental officials from Gdansk Water and Polish Water on board. They support deployment of sensors, possessing data and promoting common actions.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: Efficiency, commitment, and governance of the Living Lab are the main concerns for Gdansk.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Long-term sustainability focuses on turning risks into potentials by better identifying stakeholders and involving them at the beginning stage, reaching to 'normal' case study residents in the local communities in language and terms they can relate to, and fostering personal relationships.

4.3.4 Leipzig, Germany

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: No knowledge or experience.
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Leipzig acknowledges Living Labs as innovative spaces, but they lack hands-on experience.
- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Develop and implement local climate adaptation strategies with various stakeholders.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: The Living Lab is intended to continue after the completion of the project and to have an impact on the civil society, and politics beyond the Living Lab itself.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Foster relationships between government, citizens, and stakeholders to influence policy development.
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Create and build collaborations with different stakeholders.
- LL Methodology:
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: Develop Leipzig climate adaptation plan by collaborating with both the public and private sectors, at the same time, securing the funding support.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: Have a draft plan to conduct a series of meetings with key local stakeholders, including government officials, private sector representatives, civil society organisations, and community members.
 - ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Leipzig faces challenges of insufficient funding support for increasing local climate resilience, lack of collaboration among different stakeholders, privatisation of local resources, and demographic issues.
 - ⇒ Co-design Plan: No knowledge & experience
 - ⇒ No plan yet. Leipzig co-design process could start with involving both public and private sectors' stakeholders to set up a focal action.
 - ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: No knowledge & experience

- No plan yet, willing to get support.
- ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: No knowledge & experience
- ⇒ No specific plan yet, only draft idea of evaluation with questionnaires.
- ⇒ Demonstrate the System: No knowledge & experience
- ⇒ No plans currently exist on this.
- ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: No knowledge & experience
- Leipzig sets up the long-term goal of continuing the Living Lab and to run the Leipzig Living Lab as a model for the other cases. One of the potential scaling-up strategies is to actively engage in the Living Lab knowledge sharing platform to see how Leipzig could be a role model for the other Living Labs, potentially through policy recommendations.
- LL Management: No specific details provided, indicating that management structures for their Living Lab are still under development.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: Stakeholder fatigue, political and legal restrictions.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Long-term sustainability depends on available funding and human resources.

4.3.5 Sligo, Ireland

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: Extensive knowledge & experience
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Sligo Coastal City Living Lab was founded in 2021 by SCORE project and has been active in multiple collaborative projects involving a wide range of stakeholders. It uses various tools and methods to involve users in activities and integrates feedback through an iterative process.
- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Address coastal erosion, flooding risk, and other climate-related hazards using ecosystem-based adaptation strategies and smart technology by fostering collaboration between government, academia, citizens, and businesses.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: Focus on scalable solutions that address climate change, while fostering sustainability and international cooperation.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Refine and implement strategic roadmaps and governance structures and ensure the smooth operation of projects.
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Reinforce the stakeholder networks, identify more relevant stakeholders for PRO-CLIMATE project focus, continuously monitor and adjust strategic processes.
- LL Methodology:
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: Technological innovation to help addressing coastal erosion and flooding risks.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: A wide range of stakeholders is integrated.
 - ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Staffing resources within the local authorities, lack of awareness amongst the public about the importance of significant efforts to be applied across a range of related issues energy, resource management, etc.
 - ⇒ Co-design Plan: Some knowledge & experience
 - ⇒ Sligo has few experiences by applying various tools in co-design process but has not developed any co-design plan for PRO-CLIMATE yet.
 - ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: Extensive knowledge and experience
 - ⇒ Sligo runs real-life experimentation and testing processes to pilot innovative solutions in Living Lab under different projects.
 - ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: Limited knowledge & experience
 - ⇒ Sligo has some experience followed the instruction of ENoLL to evaluate the performance of the Living Lab but has not developed a plan for PRO-CLIMATE yet, especially needs more supports and instructions regarding monitoring governance measures and behavioural change.

- ⇒ Demonstrate the System: Some knowledge & experience.
Sligo demonstrates the use of technology in improving public awareness about local climate issues.
- ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: Limited knowledge & experience
- ⇒ Sligo Living Lab has a draft plan to upscale the solution but with certain pre-conditions, including the developed innovative technology can identify efficient ways to protect sand dune habitats, then these can be used anywhere that these habitats exist or under the same risks.
- LL Management: Sligo has detailed management strategies in place.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: Ongoing useful input from the technological innovation, active engagement of all stakeholders.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Long-term sustainability depends on ensuring adequate funding and appropriate expertise, while also ensuring that effective communication exists between all stakeholders.

4.3.6 Zakynthos, Greece

- LL Experience:
 - ⇒ Knowledge Level: Extensive knowledge and experience.
 - ⇒ Experience Details: Zakynthos Living Lab involves a wide range of stakeholders, indicating that the local team has extensive experience working with Living Labs, particularly in sustainable resource management.
- LL Objectives:
 - ⇒ Primary objectives: Sustainable tourism and sustainable resource use.
 - ⇒ Long-term objectives: Adopt an adaptation plan/strategy, subject to ongoing needs and challenges. Promote the adaptation plan and related solutions/actions to as many stakeholders as possible.
 - ⇒ Medium-term objectives: Co-create a common vision with the involved stakeholders and come up with applicable solutions regarding climate adaptation in real-time. Consideration will be given among others, to the adoption of sustainable initiatives for example regarding water savings, diversification of the existing tourism product and increase of the attractiveness of the destination (e.g., development of thematic tourism beyond the sun, sea, sound model, extension of the tourism period beyond the summer months, etc.).
 - ⇒ Short-term objectives: Collect the relevant data for setting up the Living Lab, build collaborations with different stakeholders, create urgency towards sustainable tourism and climate change adaptation
- Methodology:
 - ⇒ Scoping and Selecting a Practice: Working towards building the sustainable profile of the island's tourism industry in the context of climate adaptation.
 - ⇒ Integrate Stakeholders: Zakynthos already had a thorough mapping of the main groups of stakeholders and had in-depth interviews with key stakeholders.
 - ⇒ Uncover Barriers: Insufficient coordination and cooperation between private sector, public sector, and local communities. Lack of a common vision regarding the tourism product and of a broad adoption of sustainability as a collective social value.
 - ⇒ Co-design: Extensive knowledge & experience
 - ⇒ Zakynthos has extensive knowledge of co-design tool uses.
 - ⇒ Pilot an Intervention: Extensive knowledge & experience (previously engaged in testing & prototyping activities at more than 2 Living Labs)
 - ⇒ Evaluate Performance and Impact Assessment: Some knowledge & experience (previously engaged in evaluation activities at other Living Labs)

- ⇒ Zakynthos currently has few key ideas in this step.
- ⇒ Demonstrate the System: Extensive knowledge & experience (previously engaged in implementation activities at more than 2 Living Labs)
- ⇒ Zakynthos has drafted a plan to accomplish this step.
- ⇒ Scaling-up the Solution: Extensive knowledge & experience (has previously engaged in replicating and scaling-up activities at more than 2 Living Labs)
- ⇒ Zakynthos has clear ambition to scale up the outcomes of the Living Lab.
- LL Management: Zakynthos has management strategies in place, given their stakeholder engagement, but a detailed plan has not been developed yet.
- Challenges, Risks and Long-term Sustainability:
 - ⇒ Challenges: Build the networks with different stakeholders at the beginning and further maintain in-depth dialogues with stakeholders to ensure long-term commitment engagement.
 - ⇒ Sustainability: Zakynthos LL sustainability depends on securing funding sources, future political will and commitment, effective communication and consensus-building among stakeholders.

4.4 Data management, and contributions, and limitations

The data management process for Deliverable 2.1 (Baseline assessment and data gathering), was guided by the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Data from the six Living Labs (Sligo, Leipzig, Bergen, Badajoz, Gdansk, Zakynthos) were gathered primarily through baseline questionnaires and bilateral meetings. This dataset forms the foundation for the pilot operational plans and the strategic framework for the Living Labs. The focus is on collaboration with stakeholders, particularly in terms of identifying governance and behavioural changes for systemic transformation.

Each Living Lab contributed to this deliverable through:

- Baseline Questionnaires: Collecting insights on the state of Living Lab activities, current challenges, and stakeholder involvement.
- Bilateral Meetings: In-depth discussions with local stakeholders to validate and expand on the information gathered via the questionnaires. This contributed to a deeper understanding of local dynamics, governance structures, and climate challenges.

The primary focus was placed on gathering and consolidating baseline data to develop systemic climate resilience strategies. This data collection phase involved identifying relevant stakeholders from different sectors—public, private, NGO, and research—in each Living Lab location.

- Data Collected: Information related to Living Lab governance structures, stakeholders, climate challenges, and existing resources.
- Tools Used: Online surveys, transcripts, workshop data, and bilateral meeting notes. These datasets are crucial for defining Living Lab objectives and plans.

The collected data will support the formulation of pilot operational plans (POPs) and inform the behavioural change strategies essential for scaling up Living Lab solutions across different European contexts. While the data collected from the six Living Labs is robust, several limitations need to be acknowledged:

- **Data Completeness:** Some Living Labs, such as Bergen, Leipzig, and maybe Badajoz, are in the early stages of stakeholder engagement, leading to incomplete datasets regarding governance structures and stakeholder involvement.
- **Capacity for Co-Creation:** Not all Living Labs have fully developed co-creation methodologies, limiting the richness of the co-design data collected.
- **Lack of Unified Governance Metrics:** A major limitation is the lack of standardised Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across the Living Labs, which complicates cross-comparative analysis of governance and behavioural change.

5 Operational Expertise and Sustainability Strategy

5.1 Summary of relevant experience within the project team

Figure 14 shows the relevant activities in each stage of the PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab Framework, associated with different Work Packages. Besides the WPs shown in this figure, another two WPs - WP1 and WP7 - are leading to set and coordinate project activities and carry out financial and administrative management of the project, as well as to disseminate the project results and relevant communication with external stakeholders and interested parties.

Figure 14 Each PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab Framework stage related activities associated with different WPs

A summary of relevant expertise and experience associated with each WP can be found in the PRO-CLIMATE project Grant Agreement.

5.2 Capacity Building: Gaps and Recommendations

The success of the six Living Labs (LLs) in the PRO-CLIMATE project—Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Bergen (Norway), Badajoz (Spain), Zakynthos (Greece), and Gdansk (Poland)—hinges

on effectively building local capacity to address climate resilience challenges. Capacity building involves, not only the technical training of stakeholders, but also fostering the skills, knowledge, and institutional frameworks needed to support long-term sustainable practices in each case study. This sub-chapter identifies gaps in capacity building across the Living Labs and provides tailored recommendations to address these challenges.

5.2.1 Identified Gaps in Capacity Building

5.2.1.1 Technical Expertise and Knowledge

One of the most significant gaps identified across the six Living Labs is the lack of specialised technical knowledge and expertise in climate resilience, particularly among local stakeholders:

- **Gaps in Coastal and Marine Knowledge:** In Sligo, there is a shortage of local technical expertise related to coastal erosion, marine ecosystems, and nature-based solutions for protecting coastal communities. Stakeholders, particularly in local governments and civil society, require advanced training in these areas.
- **Urban Climate Adaptation Skills:** In Leipzig and Bergen, while there is some understanding of urban climate challenges, local officials and businesses lack sufficient knowledge in urban mitigation and flood risk management.
- **Data Management and Analysis:** Many stakeholders, across all six Living Labs, lack the ability to manage and analyse climate-related data. This gap hinders their ability to make data-driven decisions on climate resilience strategies, particularly in Gdansk, where monitoring coastal flooding risks is essential.

5.2.1.2 Community Engagement and Communication Skills

- **Insufficient Skills in Co-Creation:** Stakeholders in Badajoz and Zakynthos have limited experience in co-creation methods that bring together diverse voices in climate resilience planning. This gap hampers efforts to engage local communities in the process of co-designing solutions, a critical part of the Living Lab model (Puerari et al., 2018).
- **Low Public Awareness and Engagement:** In some Living Labs, there is a general lack of public awareness about climate change and its local impact. This gap is especially evident in Badajoz, where citizens are not sufficiently engaged in climate resilience actions, limiting their participation in Living Lab activities (Schuurman et al., 2017).

5.2.1.3 Institutional and Organisational Capacity

- **Limited Capacity for Policy Integration:** While some Living Labs, such as those in Leipzig and Bergen, have relatively advanced climate policies, there is a gap in integrating climate resilience strategies into local policy frameworks in Sligo, Badajoz, and Zakynthos. Local governments lack the capacity to institutionalise Living Lab outputs into formal planning processes (Mastelic, 2019).
- **Weak Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration:** Collaboration between academia, government, industry, and civil society is often fragmented, particularly in Gdansk. This results in a lack of coordination and inconsistent implementation of climate resilience strategies (Arnkil et al., 2010).

5.2.2 Recommendations for Addressing Capacity Building Gaps

To ensure the long-term success of the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs, it is essential to address these capacity-building gaps through targeted interventions.

5.2.2.1 Technical Training and Knowledge Development

- **Climate Resilience Training Programs:** Implement comprehensive training programs for local stakeholders, including government officials, community leaders, and businesses. These programs should cover coastal resilience (for Sligo), sustainable tourism (for Zakynthos), urban climate adaptation (for Leipzig and Bergen), and data management (for

Gdansk and Badajoz). Training should be delivered through workshops, online courses, and peer-to-peer knowledge exchanges (Brown & Katz, 2011).

- **Citizen Science Initiatives:** Establish citizen science programs, where community members are trained to collect and monitor environmental data, such as water levels in Gdansk or soil quality in Badajoz. This approach, not only builds technical capacity, but also fosters community ownership of climate resilience efforts (Ayala et al., 2022).

5.2.2.2 Enhancing Co-Creation and Public Engagement

- **Capacity Building in Co-Creation:** Provide targeted training in co-creation methodologies for local stakeholders in Zakynthos and Badajoz. Workshops focusing on participatory design and scenario planning will help stakeholders engage citizens in developing local solutions to climate challenges (Puerari et al., 2018).
- **Public Awareness Campaigns:** Launch local public awareness campaigns to educate communities on the impacts of climate change. In Badajoz, a focus on water conservation and drought-resistant agricultural practices could help engage farmers, while in Zakynthos, water scarcity campaigns could raise awareness among tourism stakeholders.

5.2.2.3 Institutional Capacity Building

- **Policy Integration Support:** Provide local governments with the tools and resources needed to integrate climate resilience strategies into broader urban and regional planning frameworks. In Sligo and Badajoz, for example, municipal staff should be trained in using policy-sandboxing tools to test and refine local climate adaptation policies.
- **Strengthening Quadruple Helix Collaboration:** In Living Labs, where collaboration between academia, government, industry, and civil society is weak, targeted efforts should be made to strengthen multi-stakeholder cooperation. For example, in some of the cases, the local government could partner more closely with Atlantic Technological University and industry players to foster innovation in climate resilience.

5.2.2.4 Knowledge Transfer and Networking

- **Cross-Living Lab Knowledge Exchange:** Organise regular knowledge-sharing events that bring together stakeholders from all six Living Labs. These events could facilitate the transfer of best practices in areas like urban heat mitigation, coastal protection, and community engagement. For example, Leipzig and Bergen could share their urban resilience strategies with Zakynthos and Sligo.
- **Regional and International Networks:** Encourage the Living Labs to become part of regional and international networks such as the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). These networks offer access to valuable resources, expertise, and partnerships that can strengthen local capacity-building efforts and provide opportunities for external funding (ENoLL, 2018).

5.2.3 Monitoring and Evaluation of Capacity Building Efforts

To ensure the effectiveness of capacity-building initiatives, it is important to establish a monitoring and evaluation framework:

- **Performance Indicators:** Define clear indicators to measure progress in capacity building, such as the number of stakeholders trained, public awareness levels, and the integration of climate resilience strategies into policy frameworks.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Create feedback loops, where stakeholders can assess the effectiveness of the training programs and provide input for improvements. Regular evaluations will ensure that capacity-building efforts remain relevant and impactful (Ayala et al., 2022).

Capacity building is a critical component of ensuring the long-term success of the Living Labs in the PRO-CLIMATE project. Addressing gaps in technical expertise, community engagement,

institutional capacity, and collaboration, the project can empower local stakeholders to take ownership of climate resilience efforts. A comprehensive approach that combines technical training, public engagement, policy integration, and knowledge sharing will, not only enhance the operational effectiveness of the Living Labs, but also ensure their sustainability beyond the project lifecycle.

6 Conclusions

The PRO-CLIMATE project aims to enhance climate resilience in diverse urban environments by establishing Living Labs (LLs) across six cases: Sligo, Leipzig, Bergen, Badajoz, Zakynthos, and Gdansk. The baseline assessment and knowledge gathering conducted under Work Package 2 (WP2) provide a foundation for implementing and managing these Living Labs. This chapter offers a summary of key findings, recommendations for the next steps, and the implications for the overall PRO-CLIMATE project.

6.1 Summary of Key Findings

The baseline analysis revealed several critical insights that will guide the development of the six (6) Living Labs:

- **Stakeholder Engagement and Diversity:** Each case study demonstrated varying levels of readiness for stakeholder engagement, with some cases, such as Gdansk and Zakynthos, showing more advanced stakeholder involvement frameworks than others, like Badajoz and Leipzig. In Sligo, local knowledge and civic engagement emerged as significant enablers for co-creation activities. However, industry involvement remains limited in some cases, posing a potential barrier to scaling innovations.
- **Co-creation and Knowledge Gaps:** Across all Living Labs, there is strong interest in co-creation, particularly in addressing local climate challenges. However, technical and financial constraints in cases, such as Badajoz and Leipzig, suggest the need for additional capacity-building and resource allocation to ensure effective implementation of POPs.
- **Local Climate Challenges:** The analysis highlighted diverse climate challenges, ranging from citi erosion in Sligo to urban heat mitigation in Leipzig. These city-specific challenges necessitate tailored solutions and adaptive co-creation processes to ensure that innovations are both contextually relevant and sustainable.
- **Operational Readiness:** While the Living Labs in Sligo, Gdansk, and Zakynthos are well-positioned for immediate implementation, others, like Badajoz and Bergen, will require more foundational support, particularly in terms of governance structures and technical expertise.

6.2 Implications for the Overall PRO-CLIMATE Project

The insights gained from the baseline assessment will have several implications for the broader PRO-CLIMATE project:

- **Scalability of Solutions:** The success of the pilot projects in the Living Labs will provide valuable lessons for scaling solutions across other regions in Europe. Developing adaptable frameworks, PRO-CLIMATE will be able to test the scalability of nature-based solutions, governance innovations, and co-creation models (Mastellic, 2019).
- **Policy Influence:** The Living Labs will serve as experimental platforms for influencing local and regional climate policies. The results from co-creation processes, especially in cases like Gdansk and Sligo, will help shape policy recommendations that can be replicated across the EU, enhancing systemic climate resilience (Schuurman et al., 2017).
- **Long-Term Sustainability:** Finally, the project's emphasis on co-creation and multi-stakeholder engagement will ensure that the outcomes of the Living Labs are, not only technically feasible, but also socially accepted and institutionally supported. Embedding climate resilience solutions within local governance frameworks, PRO-CLIMATE aims to create lasting systemic change (Brown & Katz, 2011).

7 References

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